

Study of Foramen Transversarium: A Morphological Variation**Mridul Tripathi¹, Dilip Kumar Sudele², Gunwant R. Choudhary³**¹Assistant Professor, Dept. of Anatomy, Virendra Kumar Saklecha Govt. Medical College, Neemuch (MP)²Assistant Professor, Dept. of Anatomy, Raipur Institute of Medical Sciences, Raipur C. G.³Professor & Head, Dept. Anatomy, Zydus Medical College, Dhahod, Gujrat

Received: 25-09-2024 / Revised: 23-10-2024 / Accepted: 28-11-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr Dilip Kumar Sudele

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Foramen transversarium (FT) is the special foramen located on the cervical vertebrae's left and right transverse processes (C1 to C7) containing the vertebral vessels and sympathetic plexus.¹⁻³ It is an important and noticeable feature of the cervical vertebrae that occupies the sympathetic fibers, vertebral vein (VV), and vertebral artery (VA). Foramen transversarium gives passage to vertebral artery, vertebral vein and sympathetic plexus from inferior cervical ganglion while C7 vertebra transmits only the vein. The vertebrae of the cervical part and the proximal thoracic part of the human vertebral column are the area undergoing the most intense transformation during phylogeny, leading to many anatomical variations.

Aim: Morphometric analysis of Foramen transversarium.

Objectives: To Study Foramen Transversarium unilateral & Bilateral.

Material and Methods: All the collected cervical vertebrae were examined macroscopically for the existence of the Foramen Transversarium in the 7th cervical vertebrae and the contents passing through it on both sides. All the cervical vertebrae were studied for the presence of more than one foramen and those with double foramen were photographed. In vertebrae with double foramen, the larger foramen was taken as the main foramen and the smaller foramen as the accessory foramen (AF). Digital vernier calipers of 0.01 mm precision were used for morphometric measurements. Vertebrae with this variation were photographed and noted.

Results: Result of the 120 cervical vertebrae studied, 17 (14.1%) vertebrae were found to have double FT. Out of the 17 vertebrae, 14 vertebrae were typical and 3 were atypical cervical vertebrae.

Among the 14 typical cervical vertebrae, 11 (78.5%) vertebrae had AF on the right side, 1 (7.1%) had on left side and 2 (14.2%) had bilateral AF. Among the three atypical cervical vertebrae, 2 (66.6%) had AF on the right side and 1 (33.3%) had bilateral AF. No AF was found in atlas and axis vertebrae.

Conclusion: The present study has shown that Accessory Foramen is more common on the right side is smaller in size and is situated posterior to the main foramen. The knowledge of these variations will be useful in predicting variations in the course of the vertebral artery and will aid orthopedic surgeons for planning the posterior approach of cervical spines.

Keywords:- FT-Foramen transversarium AF- Accessory foramen, VV-Vertebral vein, VA-vertebral artery

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Foramen transversarium (FT) is the special foramen located on the left and right transverse processes of the cervical vertebrae (C1 to C7) containing the vertebral vessels and sympathetic plexus. [1-3] It is an important and noticeable feature of the cervical vertebrae that occupies the sympathetic fibers, vertebral vein (VV), and vertebral artery (VA). [4]

Foramen transversarium gives passage to vertebral artery, vertebral vein and sympathetic plexus from inferior cervical ganglion while C7 vertebra transmits only the vein. [5] The vertebrae of the cervical part and the proximal thoracic part of the human vertebral column are the area undergoing

the most intense transformation during phylogeny, leading to many anatomical variations. [6]

Many factors are involved in causing morphological variations of FT, including developmental factors, mechanical stress, size and number of anatomical structures passing through. [7] The deformity and variations of this foramen may affect the anatomical course of vascular and neural structures and consequently cause pathological conditions. This alteration leads to clinical conditions such as vertebrobasilar insufficiency, [1] hearing impairment, and neurological symptoms because of the spasm of either VA or basilar artery. [8,9]

The knowledge of morphometric parameters and variation of FT in sex, age, and the side will help in identifying FT anomalies such as vertebral artery dissection, as well as in angiography and surgical procedures such as screw fixation in the cervical region and for radiological investigations.

Material and Methods

Study Population: A total number of 106 dried cervical vertebrae of unknown age and sex were collected from the Department of Anatomy of different medical colleges.

The study was approved by the Institute Ethics Committee.

Exclusion Criteria: (i) Vertebrae with deformities and damaged foramen transversarium

Methodology: All the collected cervical vertebrae were examined macroscopically for the existence of the Foramen Transversarium in the 7th cervical vertebrae and the contents passing through it on both sides. All the cervical vertebrae were studied for the presence of more than one foramen and those with double foramen were photographed. In

vertebrae with double foramen the larger foramen was taken as the main foramen and the smaller foramen as the accessory foramen (AF).

Digital vernier calipers of 0.01 mm precision were used for morphometric measurements. . Vertebrae with this variation were photographed and noted.

Statistical Analysis: The qualitative data were expressed in proportion and percentages and the quantitative data expressed as mean and standard deviations. The difference in proportion was analyzed by using chi square test. Significance levels for tests were determined as 95% (P< 0.05)

Results

Result of the 120 cervical vertebrae studied, 17 (14.1%) vertebrae were found to have double FT. Out of the 17 vertebrae, 14 vertebrae were typical and 3 were atypical cervical vertebrae.

Among the 14 typical cervical vertebrae, 11 (78.5%) vertebrae had AF on the right side, 1 (7.1%) had on left side and 2 (14.2%) had bilateral AF (Table1).

Table 1: Frequency of double FT in cervical vertebrae

Types of vertebrae	Total No.	Double FT on right side	Double FT on left side	Bilateral Double FT
Typical cervical vertebrae	14	11	01	02
Atypical cervical vertebrae	03	02	-	01

Among the three atypical cervical vertebra, 2 (66.6%) had AF on the right side and 1 (33.3%) had bilateral AF. No AF was found in atlas and axis vertebrae.

Typical Cervical Vertebra

Among the typical cervical vertebra which had double FT on the right side, the AF was much smaller in size than the main foramen and was located posterior to the main foramen. AF was separated from the main foramen by a thin bar of bone. On the contralateral side all except two had bony spicules. These bony spicules were arising opposite to each other from the margins of the main foramen giving it a double bubble appearance as

in Fig. 1. The position of the bony spicules corresponds to the thin bar of bone separating the accessory and main foramina on the right.

Only one typical cervical vertebra had double FT on the left side, AF was smaller than the main foramen, located posterior to the large main foramen. No bony spicules were seen on the contralateral side.

Two vertebrae had bilateral double FT, in one the AF of both sides were of similar size and situated posterior to the main foramen. In other the AF of the right was smaller in comparison to the left side; AF was situated anteriorly on the left side and posteriorly on the right side.(Fig. 1)

In one of the typical cervical vertebrae, an enmeshed FT was found on the left side. It was seen that a cribriform bony plate had formed around the margins of the main foramen, significantly reducing its size. The foramen on the right side showed no variation. (Fig. 3).

Atypical Cervical Vertebra: Among the atypical vertebrae, 1 had Double FT on the right side, AF was seen posterior to the main foramen.

Only one had bilateral Double FT and the AF on both the sides was located anterior to the main

foramen. On the right side AF was considerably smaller than on the left side.

In one atypical cervical vertebrae (C7) there was absence of FT on right side. (Fig. 3)

Discussion

Foramen transversarium (FT) is a bony frame work for the vertebral artery in its course from its origin to the posterior cranial fossa. [10] It is formed by the fusion of vestigial costal element fused to the body and true transverse process of the vertebra with vertebral vessels and nerves caught between the bony parts.

Many studies have been carried out on the morphology of FT. One of the studies by Kaya et al on 22 cervical vertebrae of ancient Byzantine population, double FT was found in five (22.7%) vertebrae (unilateral in three, bilateral in two). [1]

In the study conducted by Murlimanju et al on 363 cervical vertebra only six (1.6%) showed AF. Out of that five (1.4%) had double foramen and only one (0.3%) had three foramen. [11] Similarly another studies conducted by Sharma et al found that out of 200 cervical vertebra AF were found in 16 vertebrae. They also reported between C3-C6 vertebrae incidence was higher in C6 vertebra in their study. [12]

In this study we found that out of 120 cervical vertebrae, only 17 (14.1%) showed double transverse foramina out of which 14 (11.6%) were unilateral, 3 (2.5%) were bilateral. Our results are consistent with Magi Murugan et al who also reported that (12.6%) showed double transverse foramina, (10.6%) were unilateral and (3.3%) were bilateral. [13]

Taitz et al studied 480 FT and observed that only 34 vertebrae showed doubling of FT. Out of those, only in six vertebrae (C6, C1) foramen were of equal size while in other vertebrae the accompanying foramen was of very small dimensions. [9]

Another study conducted by Agarwal et al on 160 cervical vertebra in eastern India, they found that 8 have anomalous foramen among that 4 had unilaterally, 2 bilaterally and in 1 there was asymmetry in the size of foramen. They also reported in 1 vertebra there was a bony spicule incompletely dividing the foramen. [14]

In another study Das et al examined 132 cervical vertebrae and reported double FT in two vertebrae [9]. Similarly Karau et al in their morphometric study of transverse process of atlas among Kenyans in 102 vertebrae observed double FT in four cases (3.9%), one on left side and three on the right side. [15]

In this study the main foramen and AF were separated by a thin bar of bone except in one where they were separated by a thick bar of bone. Our findings are in accordance with Wysocki et al who also found the divided foramen more commonly at C6 (45.6%). The most frequent element of division was a thin bony lamina while rarely it thought the shape of a thick slat running as a string of foramen. [10]

The vertebral vessels are a major factor in the formation of FT, so variations in the vessel can be manifested as changes in FT.[9] Double FT may be co-related to the duplication or fenestration of the vertebral artery.

The embryogenesis of vertebral artery begins at 32 days and is completed by 40 days. It is formed from the fusion of the longitudinal anastomoses that links cervical intersegmental arteries which branch from the primitive dorsal aorta. The intersegmental arteries eventually regress except for the 7th vessel which forms the proximal portion of the subclavian artery, including the origin of vertebral artery. As the connection of 7th intersegmental vessel to primitive dorsal aorta disappears, the vertebral artery is formed.¹⁶ It is speculated that multiple foramen may be related to the branches of vertebral nerve passing through them. [7]

Conclusion

The present study has shown that Accessory Foramen is more common on the right side is smaller in size and is situated posterior to the main foramen. The knowledge of these variations will be useful in predicting variations in the course of the vertebral artery and will aid orthopaedic surgeons for planning posterior approach of cervical spines.

References

1. Kaya S, Yilmaz ND, Pusat S, Kural C, Kirik A, Izci Y. Double foramen transversarium variation in ancient Byzantine cervical vertebrae: preliminary report of an anthropological study. *Turk Neurosurg* 2011;21:534-8.
2. Lamberty BG, Zivanovic S. The retro-articular vertebral artery ring of the atlas and its significance. *Acta Anat (Basel)* 1973;85:113-22.
3. Tubbs RS, Johnson PC, Shoja MM, Loukas M, Oakes WJ. Foramen arcuale: anatomical study and review of the literature. *J Neurosurg Spine* 2007;6:31-4.
4. M.M. Guerra, P.R. Fuentes, I. Roa, G. Molinet, F. Robles, I. Roa, Anatomical variations of the foramen transversarium in cervical vertebrae, *Int. J. Morphol.* 2017;35(2):719–22
5. Ellis H. *Clinical Anatomy*, 11[2] th ed. Miami, MA, Blackwell pub. 2006. pp:325-28.
6. Bailey RW. *The cervical spine*. Lea and Febiger, Philadelphia. 1974. Pp:47- 74
7. Jaffar AA, Mobarak HJ, Najm SA. Morphology of the Foramen Transversarium A Correlation with Causative Factors. *Al- Kindy Col Med. J* 2004;2:61-4.
8. S. Das, R. Suri, V. Kapur, Double foramen transversaria: an osteological study with clinical implications, *Int. Med. J.* 2005;12(4):311–3.
9. C. Taitz, H. Nathan, B. Arensburg, Anatomical observations of the foramina transversaria, *J. Neurol. Neurosurg. Psychiatr.* 1978;41(2):170–6.
10. Wysocki J, Bubrowski M, Reymond J, Kwiatkowski J. Anatomical variants of the cervical vertebrae and the first thoracic vertebra in man. *Folia Morphol.* 2003;62(4):357-63.
11. B.V. Murlimanju, L.V. Prabhu, K. Shilpa, R. Rai, K.V. Dhananjaya, P.J. Jiji, Accessory transverse foramina in the cervical spine: incidence, embryological basis, morphology, and surgical importance, *Turk. Neurosurg.* 2011; 21:384–7
12. Sharma A, Singh K, Gupta G, Srivastava S. Double foramen transversarium in cervical vertebrae an osteological study. *J Anat Soc India.* 2010;59(2):229-31.
13. Magi Murugan Murugan, M. & Verma, S. A study on variations of foramen transversarium of cervical vertebrae. *National Journal of Clinical Anatomy* 2014;3(1):4-7
14. Agrawal, D.; Mohanty, B. B.; Sethy, S.; Parija, B.; Hazary, S. K. & Chinara, P. K. Variations in foramen transversarium: an osteological study in Eastern India. *Int. J. Current Research* 2012;4(9):120-2
15. Karau PB, Odula P. Some anatomical and morphometric observations in the transverse foramina of the atlas among Kenyans. *Anat J Afr* 2013;2:61-6.
16. Ionete, C. & Omojola, M. F. Angiographic demonstration of bilateral duplication of extra cranial vertebral artery unusual course and review of literature. *AJNR Am. J. Neuroradiol.* 2006;27(6):1304-6.

